

FAYZULLA KHOJAEV

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Introduction: Fayzulla Ubaydullayevich Khojayev is a famous statesman and politician, an active participant of the Bukhara struggle, one of the leaders of the "Young bukhara " party. Chairman of the Board of Supervisors of the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic. He also later became one of the leaders of the Uzbek SSR. Fayzulla Khojayev was born in 1896 in a large merchant family of Bukhara Emirate. When he was young, he graduated from the old school and studied at the Bukhara madrasah. After studying at the Bukhara madrasah for 2 years, he studied at a private school in Moscow in 1907-1912.

After returning to Bukhara, he became a member of the "Young Bukhara" party in 1912 and the Central Committee of the party in 1913. He spent the large wealth inherited from his father to open new method schools and financially support the political activities of " Young Bukhara ". Starting from 1917, Fayzulla Khojayev and Fitrat led the left wing of the party and fought to establish a constitutional monarchy and then a democratic republic in Bukhara. Khojayev and his comrades were forced to leave Bukhara after "Young bukharas" were persecuted by the emir of Bukhara.

Khojayev was the chairman of the Turkestan Central Bureau of the revolutionary " Young bukharas " party formed in Tashkent in January 1920, the editor of the "Three day" newspaper (April-September 1920). On September 14, 1920, the government of the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic - the Council of People's Supervisors was formed, and Khojayev was elected as the head of the government. Inspector of Foreign Affairs of the USSR (1920-22), Inspector of Military Affairs (1921-24), Inspector of Internal Affairs (1922), Chairman of the Labor and Defense Council of the USSR (1922-24). Also, the chairman of the Eastern Bukhara Revolutionary Military Council (1923-24), the official representative of the People's Commissariat of Naval Affairs of the USSR for the Uzbekistan SSR (since 1925). After the emir of Bukhara was overthrown and the power passed into the hands of the Young Bukharas, Fayzulla Khojayev was elected as the head of the government. In this position, he tried to conduct an independent policy, communicate equally with Russia and foreign countries. In 1922, he went to Germany to sign contracts with foreign trading companies and

large merchants. In 1925, Khojayevev was elected chairman of the Council of People's Inspectors of Uzbekistan. In his work, he strove to implement activities that serve the economic and cultural development of the Uzbek people. Khojayevev opposed the Soviet regime's policy of restricting the activities of national intellectuals. He had to work under the pressure of the center for many years.

In 1926, he was severely persecuted by the Communist Party for the book "Materials for the History of the Bukhara Revolution" devoted to the history of Jadidism. Fayzulla Khojayevev, as the head of the government, tried to develop the national economy of Uzbekistan (cotton farming, irrigation, capital construction, cattle breeding), to develop education and culture, but he later realized that these aspirations were useless in the new colonial conditions. F. Khojayevev was repressed in 1937 and sentenced to death in Moscow on March 15, 1938. The location of his grave is unknown.

In 2018, Fayzulla Khojayevev's name was included in the list of the newly opened Repression Victims Memorial Wall in Russia. Fayzulla Khojayevev was recognized by Western historians as one of the most effective managers of the 1920s and 30s. During his time, about 400 industrial facilities were built in Uzbekistan. On September 22, 1937, Fayzulla Khojayevev's family members were imprisoned. On this day, 72-year-old Rayhon Khojayeveva, mother of Fayzulla Khojayevev, F. Khojayevev's first wife Malika Khojayeveva, second wife Fatina Petrova, and daughter Vilayat Khojayeveva were imprisoned. His mother, who could not stand the torture, died in prison in the summer of 1938. Fatina Petrova was exiled to Khakassia, Russia. Malika Khojayeveva and her daughter region Khojayeveva were in exile for many years in the regions of Ust-Kamenagorsk, Ziryanovsk, and Selo Kutexa. They returned to Uzbekistan in 1945. Later, he was forcibly transferred to Kyrgyzstan. Region Khojayeveva works in Bukhara, Samarkand, Tashkent, Krasnogorsk and Moscow archives. In 1970s and 1980s, he was the leader in the preparation of the 3-volume works of F. Khojayevev published in Russian and Uzbek languages in Tashkent. Fayzulla Khojayevev worked effectively as a statesman, historian and economist, publicist, and journalist.

He left a rich scientific heritage in Uzbek and Russian languages. In 1925-1937, he published 16 books and more than 200 articles. Khojayevev's books "Materials for the history of the Bukhara revolution" (1926), "On the history of the revolution in Bukhara and the national demarcation of Central Asia" (1932), "The economic situation in the USSR" (1924), "About young Bukharas" (1926), "News" (1926), "Printing" (1930) articles show the serious problems of the history of Uzbekistan in the first quarter of the 20th century. The work entitled

"Uzbekistan on the Rise" was published in 1936. It focuses on agriculture, industry, transport and road construction, finance, public education and health care, personnel issues and other areas in the Uzbek SSR in 1935.

Conclusion:

The country called Uzbekistan officially appeared on the world map on October 27, 1924. Before that, this name was used as the second name of the former Bukhara Khanate, but it was not the official name of the state. On this day, at the White House in Bukhara, Fayzulla Khojayev announced the formation of the new Uzbekistan Soviet Socialist Republic. With this, the official history of the Republic of Uzbekistan, even though it was part of the USSR, began. "Daryo" talks about the former leaders of Uzbekistan, who participated in the administration of the republic since 1924.

References:

1. New reflections on the life and work of Fayzulla Khojayev, T., 1997;
2. Fayzulla Khodjayev. 100 years, Navoi, 1996;
3. New history of Uzbekistan, 2 books [Uzbekistan during Soviet colonialism], T., 2000;
4. Eshonov O.E., Fayzulla Khojayev, T., 1973;
5. Hasanov M., Fayzulla Khojayev, T., 1990;
6. Bagoyev M., Fayzulla Khojayev, journalist and publicist, T., 1992;

